

Role of Iron Deficiency among Non -Anemic Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Patients: A Cross-Sectional Study at a Tertiary Care Center at Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Iron deficiency without anemia has been well-documented in heart failure, but its impact on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) remains underexplored. The association of iron deficiency with disease severity, functional status, and quality of life in COPD warrants further investigation. This study aimed to evaluate the relationship between iron deficiency and clinical outcomes in non-anemic COPD patients, comparing disease severity, functional status, and quality of life between iron-deficient and iron-replete groups. This observational, cross-sectional study included non-anemic COPD patients with no history of bleeding. Participants were classified into iron-deficient (ID) and iron-replete (IR) groups based on serum iron, ferritin, and Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC) levels. Clinical assessments included 6-minute walk distance (6MWD), spirometry and Exacerbation. Demographic data, smoking history, and hemoglobin levels were also recorded.

Materials and Methods: 110 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of COPD were enrolled at the Institute of Respiratory Diseases, Sawai Man Singh Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India. Data on demographic, clinical, Hematological and spirometry parameters were collected. Statistical analysis for qualitative data were done by applying chi square test whereas quantitative data were done by applying 't' test. Data were collected and compiled with the help of MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. A p-value of <0.05 considered as statistically significant.

Results: Iron-deficient individuals had significantly lower hemoglobin and iron levels, and higher TIBC compared to non-iron-deficient counterparts. Notably, NAID is associated with more severe grades of COPD, lower 6-minute walk distances and higher exacerbation rates, although no significant differences were observed in other respiratory parameters. These findings suggest that iron deficiency may contribute to the clinical severity of COPD and support the need for further research into the potential therapeutic benefits of addressing iron deficiency in this population.

Keywords: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, iron deficiency, non-anemic, 6-minute walk distance, exacerbation rates, quality of life.

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Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is a heterogenous lung condition characterized by chronic respiratory symptoms (dyspnea, cough, sputum production) due to abnormalities of the airways (bronchitis, bronchiolitis) and/or alveoli (emphysema) that cause persistent, often progressive airflow obstruction. COPD is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally [1], with significant implications for patients' quality of life, healthcare utilization, and survival. Comorbidities

such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and anemia often exacerbate COPD outcomes, contributing to increased morbidity and mortality. Screening for these comorbidities is crucial for managing COPD patients effectively [2]. Anemia has long been recognized as a common comorbidity in COPD, with its adverse effects on functional capacity and survival. However, in recent years, iron deficiency without anemia, or non-anemic iron deficiency (NAID), has gained

attention as a significant factor in COPD, though it has been primarily studied in other conditions like heart failure. In COPD, iron deficiency can impair oxygen transport, mitochondrial function, and muscle metabolism, which are essential for maintaining aerobic capacity [3]. Even in the absence of anemia, NAID can compromise exercise performance, exacerbate skeletal muscle dysfunction, and worsen overall health status in COPD patients [4].

Iron is vital for several biological processes, including oxygen transport, cellular metabolism, and mitochondrial respiration [5,6]. It plays a central role in maintaining aerobic metabolism, and its deficiency can limit both baseline aerobic capacity and the response to exercise. While traditional teaching emphasizes polycythemia in hypoxemic COPD, anemia, particularly iron deficiency, has emerged as a significant concern. In COPD, iron homeostasis is disrupted by systemic inflammation, a hallmark of the disease. Inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukins and tumor necrosis factor- α , increase the production of hepcidin, which impairs iron absorption and utilization. This results in functional iron deficiency, characterized by low circulating iron levels despite adequate iron stores, which further contributes to impaired oxygen delivery and muscle dysfunction [7,8].

The impact of NAID in COPD has been understudied, particularly in terms of its association with exacerbation risk and exercise intolerance. Given the critical role of iron in oxygen utilization and mitochondrial function, this study aims to evaluate the prevalence of iron deficiency in non-anemic COPD patients and explore its association with clinical outcomes, including exacerbation rates and functional capacity

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This was a hospital-based, cross-sectional study conducted at the Institute of Respiratory Diseases, Sawai Man Singh Medical College, Jaipur, and Rajasthan. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethical Committee and Research Review Board of Sawai Man Singh Medical College, Jaipur.

Study Population: The study included all patients diagnosed with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) attending the Institute of Respiratory Diseases, SMS Medical College, and Jaipur. Non-anemic patients (defined as hemoglobin ≥ 13 g/dL in males and ≥ 12 g/dL in females) were selected for evaluation.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated using a study power of 80%, an alpha error of 0.05, and an assumed prevalence of iron deficiency in COPD patients of 45.5%. Based on the calculation, 90

COPD patients were required, rounded up to 110 to account for a 10% attrition rate.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Diagnosed COPD patients (according to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease [GOLD] criteria)
- Non-anemic (Hemoglobin ≥ 13 g/dL for males, ≥ 12 g/dL for females)
- Patients willing to participate and providing written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with suspected blood loss or on anemia treatment
- Pregnant and lactating females
- Patients with malignancies
- Non-cooperative patients or those unable to complete physiological tests, including spirometry

Study Procedure: All eligible patients underwent the following assessments:

- **Detailed History and Clinical Examination:** A thorough clinical evaluation was performed to assess symptoms and comorbidities.
- **Iron Studies:** Serum iron, Total Iron Binding Capacity (TIBC), and ferritin levels were measured to categorize patients into iron-deficient (ID) and non-iron-deficient (NID) groups.
- **Arterial Blood Gas Analysis:** Blood gases were measured to assess oxygenation and carbon dioxide levels.
- **Pulmonary Function Tests:** Spirometry was performed to measure Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second (FEV1), and the FEV1/FVC ratio.
- **Six-Minute Walk Test:** Performed according to the American Thoracic Society (ATS) guidelines to assess functional capacity.
- **Chest X-ray:** A chest radiograph was obtained to rule out other lung pathologies.
- **Additional Investigations:** Any other tests deemed necessary based on individual clinical presentation.

Outcome Variables:

- **Demographic Profile:** Age, gender, occupation, smoking history
- **Clinical Profile:** COPD symptoms, comorbidities, and treatment history
- **Functional Status:** 6-minute walk distance (6MWD), spirometry, and arterial blood gas parameters were compared between iron-deficient and non-iron-deficient groups.

Statistical Analysis: Quantitative data were represented as mean and standard deviation, Qualitative data were represented as percentage and proportions. Data analysis involves applying

specific test for qualitative and quantitative data. Statistical analysis for qualitative data were done by applying chi square test whereas quantitative data were done by applying 't' test. A p-value of <0.05 considered as statistically significant.

Results and Observations

This study aimed to assess the clinical differences between iron-deficient and non-iron-deficient individuals with a focus on hematological parameters, iron metabolism, and functional outcomes. A total of 110 patients were included, with a mean age of 63.8 ± 10.8 years. The majority of participants were in the age group 62-71 years (32%), followed by 52-61 years (25%) and 72-81 years (23%). The cohort was predominantly male (76%), with only 24% females. [Table 1] Regarding occupation, most participants were farmers (35%), followed by drivers (17%) and stone masons (16%).

Smoking History: Regarding smoking habits, 57% of participants reported 60-79 pack years, with 20% reporting 40-59 pack years, and 15% reporting 80-99 pack years. Only 7% of patients had 0-19 pack years. Smoking history did not show a significant association with iron deficiency status, with p-values of 0.144 for males and 0.106 for females. [Table 1]

Hemoglobin and Iron Levels The study revealed significant differences in hemoglobin (Hb) levels between iron-deficient and non-iron-deficient individuals. The mean Hb level for non-iron-deficient

males was 14.5 ± 1.2 g/dL, while for iron-deficient males, it was 12.7 ± 0.32 g/dL ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, females with non-iron deficiency had a mean Hb level of 12.6 ± 0.46 g/dL, whereas those with iron deficiency had 11.7 ± 0.15 g/dL ($p = 0.003$). [Table 1]

Serum iron levels also differed significantly, with non-iron-deficient males having median levels of 133 (110-149) $\mu\text{g/dL}$, compared to 39 (34-50) $\mu\text{g/dL}$ for iron-deficient males ($p < 0.001$). For females, the difference was similarly significant, with non-iron-deficient individuals showing median levels of 128 (92.5-141) $\mu\text{g/dL}$ compared to 35 (33.5-36.5) $\mu\text{g/dL}$ for iron-deficient individuals ($p = 0.002$). Ferritin levels were markedly lower in iron-deficient individuals. Non-iron-deficient males had a median ferritin level of 240 (202-277) ng/mL, compared to 108 (92-123.5) ng/mL in iron-deficient males ($p < 0.001$). Among females, the difference was even more pronounced: 234 (162.5-263) ng/mL versus 23 (21.5-24.5) ng/mL ($p = 0.03$). In contrast, Total Iron-Binding Capacity (TIBC) was significantly higher in iron-deficient individuals. Non-iron-deficient males had a median TIBC of 317 (275-350) $\mu\text{g/dL}$, whereas iron-deficient males had 498 (465-532) $\mu\text{g/dL}$ ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, for females, TIBC was higher in iron-deficient individuals (522 (508-540) $\mu\text{g/dL}$ vs. 350 (333-375) $\mu\text{g/dL}$, $p < 0.001$) [Table 1].

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of patients

Characteristic	All patients (n=110)	Non-iron deficient (NID)	Iron deficient (ID)	p value	Non-iron deficient (NID)	Iron deficient (ID)	p-value
		Male (n=57)	Male (n=27)		Female (n=23)	Female (n=3)	
Age	63.8 ± 10.8	63.28 ± 10.69	64.56 ± 11.1	0.614	64.35 ± 11.67	63.67 ± 8.02	0.923
Smoking pack years	58.22 ± 20.1	60.32 ± 14	64 ± 8.7	0.144	43.91 ± 32.85	76.67 ± 15.28	0.106
Hb (g/dl)	13.61 ± 1.4	14.5 ± 1.2	12.7 ± 0.32	<0.001*	12.6 ± 0.46	11.7 ± 0.15	0.003*
Fe ($\mu\text{g/dl}$) (Median(Q1-Q3))	114(51.25-141)	133(110-149)	39(34-50)	<0.001*	128(92.5-141)	35(33.5-36.5)	0.002*
Ferritin (mcg/l)	216 (122.25-255.75)	240(202-277)	108(92-123.5)	<0.001*	234(162.5-263)	23(21.5-24.5)	0.030*
TIBC ($\mu\text{g/dl}$)	350(300-456.75)	317(275-350)	498(465-532)	<0.001*	350(333-375)	522(508-540)	<0.001*

Functional Parameters: The 6-minute walk distance (6MWD) was significantly reduced in iron-deficient individuals. The overall mean 6MWD was 426.91 ± 136.9 meters, with males in the non-iron-deficient group walking significantly farther (567.2 ± 51.85 meters) compared to their

iron-deficient counterparts (312.6 ± 97.3 meters, $p < 0.001$).

Similarly, females with non-iron deficiency had a 6MWD of 491.21 ± 132.82 meters, while iron-deficient females walked only 336.67 ± 46.2 meters ($p < 0.001$). [Table 2] Spirometry results showed

no significant differences in forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1), arterial oxygen tension (PaO₂), arterial carbon dioxide tension (PaCO₂), or oxygen saturation levels (SaO₂, SpO₂) between iron-deficient and non-iron-deficient groups. The mean FEV1 across all participants was 67.42 ± 6.58%, with no significant differences in FEV1 between the two groups (p = 0.53 for males and p = 0.76 for females). Likewise, PaO₂, PaCO₂, SaO₂, and SpO₂ did not show significant associations with iron deficiency, with p-values ranging from 0.07 to 0.67. [Table 2]

Exacerbation Rates and GOLD Classification:

Exacerbation rates in the past year showed a significant association with iron deficiency status. Of the total cohort, 63 patients had no exacerbations, 34 had one exacerbation, and 13 had two. Notably, males with iron deficiency had a higher frequency

of exacerbations, with 14 individuals having one exacerbation and 13 having two, compared to males with non-iron deficiency, where 49 had no exacerbations, and only 8 had one. A similar pattern was observed in females. In total, iron-deficient patients exhibited a higher frequency of exacerbations (p < 0.001 for males and p = 0.002 for females). [Table 2]

GOLD group E classification, which represents patients with severe disease, was also significantly more prevalent in iron-deficient individuals. Among all patients, 33.6% were classified as GOLD group E, but iron-deficient males were more likely to fall into this group (24.5%) compared to non-iron-deficient males (1.8%, p < 0.001).

The proportion was also higher among iron-deficient females (2.73%) compared to non-iron-deficient females (1.82%, p = 0.003). [Table 2]

Table 2: Comparison of functional status, spirometry and arterial blood gas parameters in non-iron deficient (NID) and iron deficient (ID) groups

Characteristic	All patients (n=110)	Non-iron deficient (NID)	Iron deficient (ID)	P-value	Non-iron deficient (NID)	Iron deficient (ID)	p-value
		male (n=57)	male (n=27)		Female (n=23)	Female (n=3)	
6MWD (Mean ± SD)	426.91 ± 136.9	567.2 ± 51.85	312.6 ± 97.3	< 0.001*	491.21 ± 132.82	336.67 ± 46.2	<0.001*
FEV1 (% predicted)	67.42 ± 6.58	68.01 ± 6.72	67 ± 7.43	0.53	66 ± 5.5	67 ± 3.6	0.76
Patients in GOLD group E n (%)	343 (33.6%)	2(1.8%)	27 (24.5%)	< 0.001*	2 (1.82%)	3 (2.73%)	0.003*
PaO₂ (mm Hg)	80.85 ± 6.86	80.67 ± 5.5	79.18 ± 7.3	0.301	82.30 ± 3.85	81.33 ± 1.15	0.67
PaCO₂ (mm Hg)	41.13 ± 6.20	40.21 ± 6.0	41.55 ± 3.2	0.28	38.43 ± 8.12	44.33 ± 2.08	0.23
SaO₂ (%)	91.64 ± 2.67	92.75 ± 2.9	91.3 ± 4.2	0.07	92.87 ± 2.3	89.67 ± 4.34	0.051
SpO₂	92.99 ± 3.42	92.14 ± 3.5	90.92 ± 2.8	0.117	95.26 ± 2.45	93.67 ± 1.52	0.28
Exacerbation in a year							
0	63	49	0	<0.001*	18	0	0.002*
1	34	8	14		5	3	
2	13	0	13		0	1	

Discussion

The current study sheds light on the relationship between iron deficiency and key clinical parameters in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Our findings reveal notable trends in patient demographics, smoking habits, occupational exposure, hematological parameters, and clinical outcomes, particularly the impact of iron deficiency on functional capacity and exacerbation rates. The analysis contributes to the growing body

of literature on the multifaceted role of iron metabolism in COPD and offers insights into the potential clinical implications of iron deficiency in this population.

The study cohort predominantly consisted of older adults (ages 62-71 years), with a significant male predominance (76%). These demographic trends are consistent with previous studies in COPD populations, where older age and male gender are common characteristics Sarkar et al. (2015) [9]; Negi et

al. (2014) [10]. The higher prevalence of COPD in older males is likely linked to long-term smoking habits, which have been historically more prevalent among men John et al. (2005) [11]. This demographic trend underscores the need for gender-specific approaches to COPD management, particularly in male-dominated populations, where the severity and comorbidities, including anemia, may be more pronounced.

Our cohort was predominantly composed of farmers and drivers, occupations associated with significant exposure to environmental pollutants and respiratory irritants. Previous studies Pizzini et al. (2020) [12]; Rice et al. (1999) [13] have linked such occupations to exacerbated respiratory conditions, including COPD. These findings suggest that occupational exposures could contribute to both the development and worsening of COPD, potentially influencing iron deficiency due to chronic inflammation and increased metabolic demands. The impact of occupational exposure on iron metabolism warrants further investigation, especially in labor-intensive jobs where nutritional depletion might further exacerbate the risk of anemia.

The study observed a high prevalence of smoking in our cohort, with a mean smoking history of 58.22 pack-years. Although smoking is known to exacerbate respiratory diseases and contribute to anemia Spivak et al. (2002) [14], our analysis did not reveal a significant correlation between smoking history and iron deficiency. This finding contrasts with some previous studies Krishnan et al. (2006) [15]; Nickol et al. (2015) [16] that have suggested a more direct link between smoking and iron deficiency in COPD.

The lack of a significant association in our study highlights the complex interplay of factors influencing iron metabolism in COPD, suggesting that other variables, such as inflammation, nutritional status, and comorbidities, may play a more prominent role in iron deficiency than smoking alone. This calls for further research to identify the key determinants of iron deficiency in COPD, as smoking history alone may not fully account for the observed anemia in these patients.

A key finding in our study was the significant difference in hemoglobin levels between iron-deficient and non-iron-deficient patients, consistent with previous research Robalo Nunes et al., (2017) [17]; Chellan & Paul. (2010) [18]. Iron-deficient patients exhibited lower hemoglobin levels, with males averaging 12.7 g/dL and females 11.7 g/dL.

These findings corroborate the hypothesis that iron deficiency contributes significantly /iron deficiency and decreased hemoglobin levels underscores the importance of regular screening for iron status in COPD patients, particularly older individuals and those with comorbid conditions, who may be at

greater risk for anemia. Moreover, our analysis of iron metabolism indicators—iron levels, ferritin, and total iron-binding capacity (TIBC)—revealed significant disparities between iron-deficient and non-deficient patients.

Iron-deficient individuals had markedly lower iron levels (39 µg/dL for males, 35 µg/dL for females) and elevated TIBC, consistent with the findings of Rathi et al. (2020) and other studies Vasquez & Logomarsino (2015) [19]. Elevated TIBC serves as a compensatory response to iron deficiency, as the body attempts to increase iron absorption and mobilization. These findings reinforce the clinical utility of these biomarkers in diagnosing and managing iron deficiency in COPD patients. One of the most striking findings in our study was the significant reduction in 6-minute walk distance (6MWD) among iron-deficient patients.

This result is in line with previous studies Pizzini et al. (2020) [12]; Valderramas et al. (2013) [20], which have shown that iron deficiency can impair exercise capacity in COPD patients. Iron plays a crucial role in oxygen transport and energy metabolism, and its deficiency can lead to reduced endurance and physical capacity. The association between reduced 6MWD and iron deficiency suggests that addressing iron status could be a potential intervention to improve functional capacity and quality of life in COPD patients.

Additionally, our study found a higher frequency of exacerbations in iron-deficient patients, with significant differences in exacerbation rates between genders. This finding aligns with previous studies John et al. (2005) [11]; Kollert et al. (2013) [21] that have linked anemia, particularly iron deficiency, with increased exacerbation rates and poorer health outcomes in COPD patients. Iron deficiency may contribute to exacerbations through multiple mechanisms, including impaired oxygen delivery, systemic inflammation, and reduced muscle function. These results emphasize the need for targeted interventions to manage iron deficiency in COPD, particularly in patients with a history of frequent exacerbations or poor functional capacity.

Conclusion

We conclude that iron-deficient individuals had significantly lower hemoglobin and iron levels, and higher TIBC compared to non-iron-deficient counterparts. Notably, NAID is associated with more severe grades of COPD, lower 6-minute walk distances and higher exacerbation rates, although no significant differences were observed in other respiratory parameters. Therefore to improve patient outcome, further research is warranted to establish the efficacy and safety of iron supplementation in COPD treatment, which may lead to a significant advancement in clinical practice.

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